

Impact of Impostor Phenomenon on Psychological Distress: Self-doubt of University Students regarding Online Classes Management in COVID-19

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 11, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: September 13, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Self-doubt, Online Classes, Impostor Phenomenon, Psychological Distress</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7076307</p>	<p><i>With online classes amid the pandemic, students came across many challenges. This study aimed to find out the impact of the impostor phenomenon on psychological distress among university students. Along with that, the students were asked about their perception of self-doubt while engaging in online classes. The sample included 332 university students and the study method was a survey-based questionnaire design. For assessment measures, they were asked to fill the demographic sheet along with 2 standardized scales. The results indicated that impostor phenomenon emerged as a significant positive predictor of psychological distress. Additionally, it was observed that psychological distress and impostor phenomenon were significantly observed among those students who reported self-doubt while managing online classes amid a global pandemic. The study results contribute to Students' mental health which holds magnificent value in society and the teachers along with significant concerned people with education who constantly look into the factors that could influence their performance..</i></p>

Introduction

Through literature, it is observed that students with low psychological health are more prone to failure in their academic setup. Many students were also reported to have higher psychological distress prior to their dropout status (Jaisooriya et al., 2017; Ishii et al., 2018 as cited in Granieri et al., 2021). Chrisman and colleagues (1995) observed that people with impostor feelings are relatively associated with prolonged sadness in addition to the loss of energy and interest. Additionally, they discovered a reasonable degree of association between impostor feelings and major components of depressive somatology. For such reasons, the educational counseling cells and mental health professionals have greater responsibility to tackle the possible threats that hinder students' academic functioning (Granieri et al., 2021). It is pertinent to study those factors which affect the psychological state of university students who are taking classes (online, on-campus or hybrid form) amid a global pandemic.

Psychological Distress

In the light of Psychiatric classification of diseases, the stature of psychological distress is not clear and under scientific literature, it has been under major discussions and lengthy debates. From another perspective, the term psychological distress has been seen as emotional suffering which has a certain effect on an individual daily routine encapsulating the social domain of life. On the same side, the topic under discussion is an area of interest for many studies under which the possible etiological and precautionary aspects are deemed to explore. Speaking diversely, the term distress is being used in many psychological disorders as a diagnostic symptom (e.g., PTSD and OCD) and further as an indicator of suffering estimation in routine functioning (e.g., GAD and MDD). Therefore, it is an alarming situation in the medical field when such emotional and psychological stress is accompanied by other symptoms and then further involved in becoming a diagnostic criterion for mental-related disorders. While the stress-distress model presents its notion, the psychological distress is observed as a short-term, temporary occurrence involving "usual and standard" emotional response against some stressful event. In 2007, this note was demonstrated by Horowitz by pointing out a number of papers which studied the adolescents and in those series of study a high variation of depression-based symptoms were observed which tend to become reduced in a period of 4 weeks. According to him, such variation in emotional symptoms displays the transient grief which can stem from flunking the quiz, not being able to win some sports activity or losing one's intimate partner. Such temporary phenomenon of psychological distress was opposed by some theorists which includes Wheaton along with his co-workers (2007 as cited in Drapeau et al., 2012). They examined the consistency of psychological distress phenomenon in 7 longitudinal studies which were conducted on adults over 10 years. According to their findings, psychological distress was comparatively consistent and they asserted that such findings negate the "transient nature" postulation of distress. Over the period of time, they could not account for the personality role for the stable course of psychological distress. Moreover, psychological distress

has been reportedly aligned with neuroticism and some proclaim that it might be slightly responsible for distress which is persistent and long-term (Drapeau et al., 2012).

Generally psychological distress is explained as psychological health issue which is more arbitrary oriented, having no firm specification. On contrary, Wheaton (2007 as cited in Drapeau et al., 2012) suggested to raise the issue of such non-specific element attached to its nature as psychological distress had been clearly assigned with the symptoms of anxiety and depression. The link between psychological distress and depression along with low degree with anxiety directs the debate whether things would remain same in such disorders if distress element is neglected in terms of treatment. Regrettably, the itinerary of such distress mostly happens to be unspecified. Lastly, the psychological distress definition as emotional reaction which is considered as normal under stressful event creates issue across discrete situations and population because of the word "normal". Without a doubt, it has been largely concurred that idiographic and nomothetic reactions to disease or some other distress are slightly demarcated by societal and cultural standards. Although the indications of low mental state tends to be omnipresent i.e feeling low, being anxious and depressed, its duration along with expressions and further transformation to other emotional symptoms tend to be different transculturally. Physical and body based symptoms are mainly a significant part under such variations to emotional response across societies. In 1989, psychological distress was generally manifested in terms of somatic symptoms but the forms of such physical symptoms link with distress may vary in different cultures and society. Likely, these body based symptoms are associated to affective disorder which are manifested by being fatigue, loss of energy and sleep, inability to carryout normal functioning, low appetite and feeling of being shallow (Drapeau et al., 2012).

Impostor Phenomenon

Initially, the term "Impostor Phenomenon" was delineated by DrPaulineClance, which she presented after her observations from the clinical setup. Peoplehavingimpostor phenomenon come across with stronger feelings that their accomplishmentsare unmerited and are exceedingly concerned that most possibly they are about to reveal as deceit. Such tendencylead towardsdysfunctionalbehavior and psychological discomfort (Sakulku & Alexander, 2011).

In 1978, Clance and Imesused the phrase "Impostor Phenomenon" to explain the characteristics and performance or actions of a bunch of affluentladiesthat were troubled to owning their achievements. The samplefailed toaccredit their success to their own capabilitiesregardless of several accomplishments and wide recognitions due to which these women representedfeeling of fraudulence. Individuals with impostorphenomenonlook themselves as undeserving ofthe extent of admirationthey are receiving. The reason is thatthey do not trust such praise which is completely acquired due to their own abilities. Such disbelief further inflicts a degree of hysteria and stress among impostors(Parkman, 2016).

Impostor Phenomenon was initially perceived to solelyhave an effect oncompetent and skilledladies. But, experience of being an impostortends to be generallyacknowledged. Related research work has indicated thatImpostorismtends to affect individuals on a large scale. For instance, Impostor phenomenon has been noted to effect male and female both. Its occurrence has also been reported amongfolks with totally different professionslikeschool students, faculty, medical students, promoting managers, and assistants of medical practitioners. Additionally it has been reported that Impostor phenomenon occursthroughoutdifferentsocieties. It has been deemed that there exists seventieth percentprobability of individuals having minimally one episode of impostor phenomenduring their life span. In 1981, it wasdeclaredby Harvey that any individual can perceive themselves as having impostor feelings if they fail to recognize their own success and this feelingis notrestricted to those folks thatareextremelybooming (Sakulku & Alexander, 2011).

Individuals with the impostor phenomenoncanimply that they aretruly conscious about how others see them however that they are known about the fact that the privileges and recognitions are incorrectlyconferredupon them. That's because it was not due to their effort solely and they did not quite earnit. Peoplescuffling withImpostorism often associateaccomplishment to external factors i.e low-grade standards, corresponding and intercommunication, a factor of time, and their charisma. Alternatively, the achievement is accredited to presentation expertise thatenables them to coverthe actualessence of their performance or demonstration. Within thethoughts pattern of the people with Impostorism, slight positive but moremisunderstood perception of one's capabilityhas been formed. Keeping up such distorted perception for long time period transform into noteworthyobjectives. Other people are well aware of impostors to whom they see as succeeder and recognize their drive for additional development. Such attitude towards impostors lead other people to assign more duties to them by knowing the fact that they are going to deliver a superb performance. Unable to recognize previous accomplishments, anoutsideinfluence of management and deficiency of confidence in reproducingprevious behaviorsassociated withthe rise in visibility, results ina notable degree ofexcessive concerntypicallyrelated to excessive attention on impression management and performance with a self-evaluatingtendency (Parkman, 2016).

Literature Review

Asif and Hashmi (2020) carried out a research on University students to study the influence of COVID-19 pandemic on psychological health. The purpose of their research was to explore the psychosocial effects on University students amid global pandemic which was done cross-sectionally. During this study 1029 participants were approached in which 26.7% of students reported to mildly affected by COVID-19 pandemic, similarly 27.2% and 17.0% of students were moderately and severely affected respectively. A negative relationship was found between anxiety and stable income and with those students living in urban area with parents. A positive relationship was found between financial strain, educational system delays and range of anxiety symptoms.

Khalid et al. (2021) conducted a study which was carried through email survey. The purpose of their research was to find out the connection between Psychological distress and COVID-19 knowledge among those students who were living in quarantine. During this survey, students from different universities and colleges were approached. During analyses, the knowledge scores of students with multiple levels of psychological distress knowledge was compared by using one-way analysis variance (ANOVA). The result indicated that participants with moderate and severe mental distress scored lower than those students who reported themselves to be psychologically healthy.

Mahmood et al. (2021) conducted a study on university students to investigate the manifestation and prevalence of the most frequently reported psychosocial reactions to the COVID-19 pandemic onset. The analyses revealed that obsession with cleanliness, uncertainty about future, confined daily functioning, depressed mood and boredom were most common psychosocial reactions reported during COVID-19. The crisis related to finance was found to be least frequently reported. Furthermore, the study found that participants were reported to have mild, moderate, severe and most severe level of problems as 18%, 34%, 29% and 19% respectively. This study also highlighted the fact that mental health professionals should direct their due attention towards university students as they were found to be significantly impacted by COVID-19 pandemic.

Khawar et al. (2021) conducted a study on students from different universities. Their research work focused to inspect the predictors of online classes' satisfaction and socio-demographics predictors of psychological distress. The study also intended to explore the relationship between online classes satisfaction and psychological distress among university students amid global pandemic. The results revealed that 70% of university students reported 41.5 % to 29% of severe and mild level of distress. In addition that, a negative association was observed between online classes satisfaction and psychological distress among university students.

Purpose

The literature indicated that sudden outburst of disease have affected psychological health and contentment of individuals. In this regard many risk oriented issues were studied. This exploration led to discovery that women and students having age range of 16 to 24 years showed a higher tendency to be at risk of having the symptoms of psychological issues i.e distress (AlAteeq et al., 2020). It became a motive for current research to study those factors which would impact students' mental health and how pandemic-oriented education influences them.

Method

Research Design

The current research was carried out as correlational (cross-sectional survey) design.

Hypotheses

1. There will be a positive relationship between the impostor phenomenon and psychological distress among university students.
2. The impostor phenomenon will likely to positively predict psychological distress among university students.
3. Gender differences will likely be significant in impostor phenomenon and psychological distress among university students.
4. University students reporting self-doubt related to online classes management will have significant impostor phenomenon and psychological distress.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

332 Participants were approached through purposive sampling from different universities. Due to prevailing pandemic at time, the students were sent study link and online data was collected. The participants were provided with informed consent along with demographic sheet and questionnaires.

Inclusion Criteria

The sample was employed on the basis of following conditions

- University students taking classes (online and hybrid) amid Global Pandemic-2021.
- University students having age range of 18-28 years.

Exclusion Criteria

The understudy sample was precluded on terms of following features

- Students of post graduate colleges and schools.
- Students enrolled in special education sector
- Students enrolled in Vocational based institutes/centers

Table1.Sociodemographic Characteristics of Sample (N=332)

Demographics	<i>f</i>	%
Age		
18-20	96	28.9
21-22	176	53
23-25	43	13
26-28	17	5.1
Gender		
Female	292	88
Male	40	12
Educational Program		
BS	304	91.6
M.PHIL/MS	23	6.9
Ph.D	5	1.5
Semester		
1 st - 2 nd	21	6.3
3 rd - 4 th	142	42.8
5 th - 6 th	93	28
7 th - 8 th	76	22.9
Marital status		
Married	36	10.8
Unmarried	296	89.2
Family structure		
Joint	138	41.6
Nuclear	194	58.4
What was the mode of Education during Pandemic?		
Online	190	57.2
Online & On Campus	142	42.8
What Application you used for online education?		
LMS	85	25.6
Whats' app	7	2.1
MS team	201	60.5
Zoom Google meet	39	11.7
Are you satisfied from online education?		
Yes	101	30.4
No	231	70
Do you want online education to continue?		
Yes	70	21.1
No	270	
Did you have doubts over yourself regarding online classes (logging in/managing)?		
Yes	187	56.3
No	145	43.7

Initially,344total data was collected through online measures from which inadequate response types were omitted (as some of the students left the forms incomplete in the middle of filling the questionnaires or omit some of the questions during the study and some of them did not provide their consent to be part of the study). Such data reduction led the number to 332 among which female respondents were far more than males. The sampling was carried out during global pandemic so 57.2% of the subjects reported that they were taking an

online class and 42.8% reported hybrid classes (online and on-campus both) as their mode of education. B.S. students were far more than MS/M.Phil.andPh.D students. 30% of the sample were actually satisfied from their online education during pandemic while remaining major proportion were not in favor of such education policy, which is concurrent to the findings of Ullah et al. (2021) study. In their study, they reported that about 65% of their sample population were not fully satisfied from pandemic-induced education transformation. 25% of the sample reported that they used LMS as a source for their online education. About 56% of the sample were actually reported to have doubts over themselves in terms of managing the online mode of education which was actually more than half of the current sample size. During this stage, more than 60% of the students reported something which was due their subjective concern that their academic achievement scores were dropped as a result of the online education system.

Demographic Sheet

The participants were initially asked about general information which included age, gender, education program with the semester, marital status and family structure. Along with such basic details, the participants were also inquired about the information which were relevant to the current study variables and pandemic based education. i.e. “How many friends do you have”, “What was your mode of education during pandemic”, “Do you want to continue online education”, “Did you have doubts over yourself regarding online classes (logging-in/managing)” etc. For Psychological Distress, Kessler et al.(2002) scale was used. The K-10 Psychological Distress Scale comprises of 10 statements with 5 point likert version. The respondents are asked to provide their responses in accordance to past 4 week’s timeframe. For evaluating the tendency or experiences related to impostor feelings and if indicated in individuals then to assess its level of severity, Clance (1985) developed a scale. Overall, the CIPS included 20 items and it was a 5-point rating scale which range from 1 Not true at all to 5 Very true. Primarily, the CIPS comprised of three subscales: The Luck (item no. 5, 9, 11, 15), Discount subscale (item no. 10, 16, 19) and Fake subscale (item no. 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 12, 13, 14, 17, 18, 20). A higher score on CIPS indicates a greater tendency of feeling like being a fraud or an impostor.

Results

In order to analyze current study data with respect to defined objectives, sample demographics characteristics, descriptive statistics of the study variables, internal consistencies of the instruments used, and correlation of the study variables were examined. Along with that independent t-test and linear regression analysis were carried out. The following tables provide descriptive for the current study variables.

In table 2, the descriptive statistics were analyzed for all variables under study.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Study Major Variables (N=332)

Variables	Items	M	S.D	α	Range		Skewness	Kurtosis
					Actual	Potential		
K-10PDS	10	30.22	9.36	0.89	10-50	10-50	-.12	-.65
CIPS	20	66.12	13.55	0.86	27-100	20-100	-.08	.35
Fake	11	36.53	8.74	0.83	11-55	11-55	-.23	-.34
Luck	4	13.31	3.32	0.5	4-20	4-20	-.01	-.29
Discount	3	9.41	2.85	0.6	3-15	3-15	.09	-.34

Note: PDS=K-10 Psychological Distress Scale, CIPS= Clance Imposter Phenomenon scale, DNT=Discount, M=Mean, SD= Standard deviation, α =Cronbach’s Alpha

To determine the relationship between psychological distress and impostor phenomenon, Pearson product moment correlations was carried out.

Variables	1	2	3	4	5
1 Psychological Distress	-	.55**	.55**	.29**	.43**
2 Impostor Phenomenon		-	.95**	.72**	.74**
3 Fake			-	.55**	.59**
4 Luck				-	.49**

Table 5
between 5 Discount - 3.Relationship Psychological
Distress and Imposter Phenomenon (N=322)

Note: ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$,

A significant positive relationship was found between Psychological Distress and Imposter Phenomenon ($r = .55^{**}$, $p < .01$). Other than that a significant positive correlation was found of fake and luck subscale with psychological distress ($r = .55^{**}$, $.29^{**}$, $p < .01$). Additionally the fake subscale positively correlated with psychological distress ($r = .55^{**}$, $p < .01$). During current analyses it was also observed that there exist a positive relationship between psychological distress and luck ($r = .29^{**}$, $p < .01$) along with discount ($r = .43^{**}$, $p < .01$)

In order to find out predicting role of Imposter Phenomenon upon Psychological Distress, a linear regression was carried out.

Table 4. Predicting effect of Imposter Phenomenon on Psychological Distress (N=332)

	B	β	S.E	p	95% of Confidence Interval	
					LL	UL
Constant	23.41	-	3.61	.00	16.31	30.52
Imposter Phenomenon	.36	.54	.62	.00	.31	.43
R^2	.38					
ΔR^2	.39					
F	66.39**					

B=Beta coefficient, R= Regression Coefficient,
 $P < .00$

A significant positive impact on psychological distress was observed by Imposter phenomenon (66.39 $B = .54$, $p < .001$). 38% variance was also observed in this model which suggest that imposter phenomenon have a positive effect on the psychological distress.

In order to find gender differences between variables, independent t-test was carried out.

Table 5. Gender Difference on study major variables (N=332)

Variables	Male (n=40)		Female (n=292)		95% of Confidence Interval				Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD	t	p	LL	UL	
PD	31.35	10.38	30.06	9.22	.75	.26	-2.18	4.76	.13
IP	64	13.23	66.46	13.58	-1.1	.79	-6.96	2.01	.18
Fake	35.68	7.97	36.65	8.85	-.71	.52	-3.70	1.76	.12
Luck	12.33	3.21	13.44	3.32	-2.1	.81	-2.21	-.02	.34
Discount	9.2	2.73	9.44	2.87	-.52	.59	-1.17	.69	.09

Note: K-10 PD=Psychological Distress, IP=Imposter Phenomenon, DNT=Discount,

The values were not significant among all variables ($t = PD .75$ and Imposter Phenomenon $-.79$, $p > .05$) which indicated that such measures were same across gender (both men and women were having equal tendency). The Cohen's d values were also low among all variables.

In order to check the level of Psychological distress and Impostor Phenomenon among students reporting self-doubts regarding managing the online education system, an independent t-test was carried out.

Table 6. Psychological Distress, Imposter Phenomenon and Self-doubt regarding online classes management (N=332)

Self-doubt regarding online classes management	Yes (n=187)		No (n=145)		95% of Confidence Interval			
	M	SD	M	SD	t	p	LL	UL
Psychological Distress	31.53	9.01	28.52	9.55	2.94	.00	.99	5.02
Impostor Phenomenon	67.96	12.93	63.84	13.97	2.77	.01	1.19	7.04

Note: M=Mean, SD= Standard deviation,

It has been observed that those individuals who reported to have doubts over themselves had significant psychological distress and impostor phenomenon ($p < .05$).

Discussion

In current study, a positive relation was found between impostor phenomenon and psychological distress. Thus hypothesis I that there will likely to have a positive relationship between impostor phenomenon and psychological distress among University students was supported (table-3). The current finding was in congruent with previous studies. A study was conducted by Chrisman et al. (1995) to study depression experience and impostor fears. They found that both factors had strong positive correlation ($r = .62$) which supports current study findings. The findings reported by Sonnack & Towell (2001) also indicate that impostor fears are positively correlated to poor mental health ($r = .33$) among undergraduate students. Cokley et al. (2013, 2017) carried out research on impostor feelings and psychological distress along with depression and anxiety. They reported a positive relationship between impostor feelings and psychological distress in their sample which goes parallel to current study findings. Wei et al. (2020) carried out a research on 433 Asian Americans students in order to study the association between impostor feelings and psychological distress and how it is mediated by interpersonal shame and moderated by self-compassion. A positive association was found between impostor feelings and psychological distress was partially mediated by interpersonal shame.

The impostor phenomenon was found to be positive predictor of psychological distress from current study results. In such leau, hypothesis II that impostor phenomenon would likely to positively anticipate psychological distress was supported (table-4). Cokley et al. (2017) carried out research on ethnic students which involved impostor feelings, perceived discrimination and mental health. They reported that impostor phenomenon had stronger impact on anxiety and depression upon their sample which goes parallel to current study findings. McClain et al. (2016) carried out a study on the college black undergraduates. Their aim was to find out the factors of psychological health with perspective to impostor feelings, ethnic identity and stress of minority status. They observed that impostor feeling was strong negative anticipator of mental health.

No significant gender differences were found among current study variables. Thus the hypothesis III that gender differences would likely to be significantly observed among impostor phenomenon and psychological distress was not supported (table-5). The current study results indicated that tendency of these phenomenon were observed at equivalent levels across gender. Mangum (2018) carried out a study in Middle Tennessee to explore the possible predictors of impostor phenomenon among students. They found out no gender differences during their study which goes parallel to current study results.

The level of psychological distress and impostor phenomenon was found to be high among students who reported their self-doubt regarding online classes management (i.e. logging in) (table-6). In a study conducted by Abramenska (2015), the objectives were to explore the factors of motivation and hindrances faced by students' in online/hybrid classes. They found that those students who enrolled in one online class have experienced hurdles with in the domain of being isolated, getting proper response from instructors and state of being confused and muddled during online session, which is concurrent to current study observations. In addition to that, they reported that some of the students who took at least one online class were reluctant to take another online class. Ullah et al. (2021) studied the issues faced by Pakistani students related to pandemic based online education. In their study, they found that about 65% of the students reported that they had experienced some degree of incompetence while engaging in online class. Additionally, they observed that about 62% of the sample reported a decline in their level of confidence during this time.

Conclusion

The positive association was found between impostor phenomenon and psychological distress. Furthermore, the impostor phenomenon was observed to positively predict the psychological distress. However, no significant gender differences were reported after analyses in current study. Students who reported self-doubt related to online classes management during pandemic had significant psychological distress and impostor phenomenon.

Future Suggestions

Those students who had a history of COVID-19 should be assessed thoroughly to indicate the important factors involving online education system. Further qualitative study should be carried out to encapsulate the all details related to pandemic education.

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